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Factors Influencing the Choice of Shared Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract

The deployment of autonomous vehicles (AVs) is recognised as one of the principal strategies for improving the efficiency of transport systems and reducing costs. It is anticipated that the use of these vehicles will mitigate the negative externalities of travel related to land use, congestion, environmental degradation, and public health. Given the growing importance of AVs and their potential widespread application in the near future and considering that the initial step toward their adoption is expected to occur through shared mobility systems, this study identifies the factors influencing the choice of shared autonomous vehicles.

To this end, a set of choice scenarios was designed to compare the selection between conventional shared vehicles and autonomous shared vehicles, with varying levels of travel cost, travel time, waiting time, and vehicle type (car or van). A total of 326 responses were collected, and a **binary logit model** was used for analysis. The results indicate that the ratios of cost, travel time, and waiting time between autonomous and conventional vehicles, along with several socio-demographic variables (age, education), habitual travel patterns, perceived social norms, attitudes toward technology adoption, privacy, safety, and trust in autonomous systems, significantly influence the probability of choosing autonomous shared vehicles.

Keywords: Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), Autonomous Vehicle, Mode Choice, Discrete Choice Model, Binary Logit Model

1. Introduction

In recent years, many cities have faced the challenge of uncontrolled growth in travel demand, resulting in serious problems such as delays, congestion, fuel price increases, higher CO₂ emissions from vehicles, more accidents, and ultimately a decline in quality of life. These challenges are expected to intensify due to population growth and urban migration.

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Therefore, identifying strategies that can enhance the safety and efficiency of transport systems has become essential.

The advancement of information and communication technologies (ICT) has opened new opportunities for the development of **Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS)**. ITS technologies based on advanced wireless, electronic, and automation solutions are designed to improve the safety, efficiency, and convenience of mobility. ITS rests upon four fundamental principles: **sustainability, integration, safety, and responsiveness**. These principles play a vital role in achieving the core objectives of ITS, including accessibility, mobility, and economic growth. Furthermore, the success of ITS largely depends on the capacity to collect, access, and process environmental data effectively [1].

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) represent one of the most innovative outcomes of ITS technology. Their development is expected to bring fundamental transformations in transportation systems. By leveraging tools such as **artificial intelligence, image sensors, robotics, data security systems, and communication technologies**, AVs can significantly reduce accidents, energy consumption, pollution, and operational costs. Inevitably, their emergence will impact industries, labour markets, and regulatory frameworks industries unable to adapt may face obsolescence [2].

Nearly all major automakers, along with leading technology firms, are currently engaged in research and development projects for AVs. Automakers and tech startups are competing to become pioneers in introducing these vehicles to the public market. Experts predict that by **2030**, autonomous driving technology will be commercially accessible worldwide [3].

Currently, partially autonomous driving technologies are already available, though fully autonomous operation remains under development. Because of the potential implications for legal and policy frameworks, transport authorities have taken a cautious approach toward implementation. For instance, in 2016, the **European Union** required its member states to establish regulations allowing AVs to operate on public roads [4].

As AVs become more common, the overall driving experience will change dramatically, as users will no longer need to focus on traffic. Travellers may use travel time for reading, working, or resting. Moreover, the rise of autonomous technology enables new business models, such as **Shared Autonomous Vehicles (SAVs)**, which can provide affordable mobility solutions. Proper coordination of SAV systems could reduce congestion, lower car ownership rates, decrease parking demand, and ultimately save costs for users [5].

Recognising the importance of AV adoption in the future, this study aims to identify the key factors affecting individuals' decisions to choose these vehicles as their mode of travel. Since the first stage of adoption is expected to occur within shared transport systems, the research focuses specifically on **shared autonomous vehicles**.

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2. Previous Research

The study of behavioural factors determining the decision to adopt autonomous vehicles (AVs) is inherently complex and multidisciplinary. Therefore, an interdisciplinary approach is required to examine the wide range of variables that influence the public's acceptance of AVs.

Numerous studies have addressed this subject. For example, **Sanbonmatsu et al. (2018)** explored public opinion and the long-term acceptance of autonomous transport technologies, focusing mainly on the financial aspects of driverless systems and a limited set of attitudinal variables such as safety concerns, privacy, and trust in automation [6].

In recent years, public interest and research in AV technologies have grown significantly. However, **Wu et al. (2020)** argued that behavioural and theory-based analytical approaches for identifying the key determinants of AV adoption remain insufficient. In their survey-based research, they measured users' general attitudes toward AVs. Respondents perceived AVs as environmentally friendly and particularly attractive for enabling mobility for non-drivers and reducing travel fatigue. However, concerns regarding safety and cost were identified as major barriers to adoption. They concluded that improving urban infrastructure and reducing perceived costs could enhance the willingness to adopt AVs [7].

A seminal contribution in this field was provided by **Acheampong and Cugurullo (2019)**, who developed conceptual frameworks and measurement models to identify behavioural determinants influencing AV adoption across ownership, sharing, and public transport contexts. They validated their framework using a structured online questionnaire (n = 507), analysing the reliability and correlation of latent variables. Their study proposed four measurement models applicable for predicting user interest and behavioural intentions toward AVs in three scenarios: ownership, shared use, and public transport [8].

Building upon that work, **Moore et al. (2020)** investigated the concept of willingness to share AVs with others. They compared the monetary value of travelling alone versus sharing rides with strangers using a multivariate integrated model of latent variables. Their results revealed that users were less sensitive to the presence of strangers during work-related trips compared to leisure trips. However, added travel time posed a greater deterrent than sharing space with others. Therefore, for high-income individuals, the ability to use travel time productively could offset this reluctance [9].

Soteropoulos et al. (2019) conducted a comprehensive review of modelling studies addressing the impact of AVs on travel behaviour and land use. Their findings highlighted the necessity of AV deployment, the extent of adoption, and usage patterns. They found that feedback effects among users spread gradually and could evolve into a new urban mobility paradigm. They also concluded that public AV fleets could substantially reduce the total number of vehicles, parking demand, and overall urban congestion. However, they emphasised that results depend heavily on model assumptions such as time spent in AVs and recommended further research to develop more robust models of AV acceptance [10].

Moody et al. (2019) further expanded on these findings by applying a multilevel structural equation model to analyse perceived AV safety among 33,958 respondents across 51

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countries. They found that younger males reported higher perceived safety and expected shorter times for AVs to reach acceptable safety levels. Countries with higher income and education levels were more optimistic about AV safety, suggesting potential global disparities in road safety perceptions [11].

Finally, another line of research has estimated optimal AV fleet sizes for shared systems, exploring potential environmental effects, land use implications, and behavioural changes associated with AV adoption [5].

The present study, drawing upon the most relevant factors identified in prior literature, seeks to examine the combined effects of socio-economic, attitudinal, and operational variables influencing individuals' preferences between **shared autonomous vehicles** and **conventional shared cars**.

3. Data Collection

This research aims to identify the determinants influencing individuals' choice of shared autonomous vehicles (SAVs) as a travel mode. The study considers variables related to socio-economic characteristics, travel patterns, and attitudes toward AVs. Data were collected via an online and in-person questionnaire, structured according to established literature.

The questionnaire included three main sections (see Table 1):

<p>Section 1 assessed respondents' attitudes toward AVs, including awareness of new technologies, technology acceptance, privacy concerns, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, safety risk, and trust. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).</p>
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<p>Section 2 introduced hypothetical mode choice scenarios, comparing a conventional shared car and an autonomous shared vehicle. Scenarios varied by vehicle type (car or van), travel time, waiting time, and fare.</p>

<p>Section 3 gathered socio-demographic and economic information, such as age, gender, marital status, education, employment, household size, driver's licence ownership, car ownership, household income, and daily travel modes.</p>
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Six hypothetical scenarios, integrating variations in fare, vehicle type, waiting time, and travel duration, were presented to each respondent (see Tables 2 and 3). Participants indicated their preferred travel mode under each scenario. The results revealed a general preference for autonomous shared vehicles, particularly when these offered clear advantages in cost and travel time. As these findings are based on stated preferences, actual choices may diverge once autonomous vehicles are widely adopted. Nevertheless, the data suggest that the introduction of autonomous vehicles could significantly reshape urban mobility patterns.

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Table 2 – Sample Scenario

Scenario 2	Conventional Taxi	Autonomous Taxi
Vehicle Type	Van	Car
Waiting Time	10 min	5 min
Travel Time	40 min	32 min
Fee	14000 Toman	16000 Toman
Your Choice		

Table 3 – Attribute Levels

Attribute	Conventional Taxi	Autonomous Taxi
Vehicle Type	Car / Van	Car / Van
Waiting Time	5 min / 10 min	5 min / 10 min
Travel Time	40 min / 48 min	32 min / 40 min
Fee	14000/18000 Toman	12000/16000 Toman

Table 4 – User Travel Mode Preferences

Variable Frequency	Frequency
Conventional Taxi	310
Autonomous Taxi	1,646
Total	1,956

Table 5 presents key socio-demographic and economic characteristics of the respondents. Most participants were aged 31–40 and held a master’s degree or higher. About 60% were male and 49% were single. More than half were full-time employees. Around 90% had a driving license, and approximately 65% owned a private vehicle. About 40% reported a monthly household income between 10–25 million Toman, and 75% had one or two cars in their household.

Table 5 – Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage	Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Age			Household Size		
<20	11	3.4	1	27	3.8
21–30	86	26.4	2	53	16.3
31–40	116	35.6	3	63	19.3
41–50	72	22.1	4	104	31.9
>50	41	12.6	≥5	79	24.1
Gender			Driving License		
Female	124	38.0	Yes	294	90.2
Male	202	62.0	No	32	9.8
Marital Status			Car Ownership		
Single	169	48.2	Yes	211	64.3
Married	157	51.8	No	115	35.0

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Table 5 – Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage	Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Employment Status			Household Income		
Student	55	16.9	<10 million Toman	26	8.0
Part-time Employee	21	6.4	10–25 million Toman	128	39.3
Full-time Employee	171	52.5	25–40 million Toman	78	23.9
Self-employed	65	19.9	40–60 million Toman	44	13.5
Unemployed	14	4.3	≥60 million Toman	50	15.3
Education Level			Number of Vehicles		
Below Diploma/ Diploma	28	8.6	0	21	4.6
Associate/ Bachelor	117	35.9	1	138	42.3
Master / PhD	181	55.5	2	107	32.8
			≥3	60	18.3

4. Mode Choice Model

Given the discrete nature of the data, a **binary logit model** was used to analyse individual choices between conventional shared vehicles and autonomous ones. The model's final results, including variable definitions and coefficients, are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 – Results of the Binary Logit Model for Autonomous Shared Vehicle Choice

No.	Significant Variables	Coefficient	Definition	p-value
1	FEEACP	-10.794	Ratio of autonomous vehicle travel cost to conventional taxi cost	0.000
2	TTACP	-3.675	Ratio of autonomous vehicle travel time to conventional taxi travel time	0.000
3	WTACP	-0.375	Ratio of autonomous vehicle waiting time to conventional taxi waiting time	0.006
4	CCT	1.722	Conventional van	0.001
5	ACT	-2.617	Autonomous van	0.000
6	ADAVG	0.248	Average score of technology adoption variable	0.034
7	SNAVG	-0.165	Average score of perceived social norm	0.097
8	PBCAVG	0.211	Average score of perceived ease of use	0.063
9	USEAVG	0.748	Average score of perceived usefulness	0.000
10	SAVG	-0.175	Average score of safety perception	0.041
11	TAVG	0.445	Average score of trust variable	0.000
12	DTV3	-0.402	Daily travel mode: taxi	0.045

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Table 6 – Results of the Binary Logit Model for Autonomous Shared Vehicle Choice

13	DTV6	-0.804	Daily travel mode: motorcycle or bicycle	0.000
14	THV	2.115	Daily travel mode: company transport service	0.000
15	AGE	-0.012	Age	0.056
16	JFT	0.403	Full-time employment	0.009
17	ED2	0.507	Education level: associate or bachelor's degree	0.001
18	DL	0.950	Possession of a driver's license	0.000
19	HHI3	-0.339	Monthly household income between 25–40 million Tomans	0.040
20	HHC	-0.289	Number of household vehicles	0.000
21	Constant	13.704		0.000
ρ^2 0.21 K 21 N 1956				

The results indicate that the ratios of **travel cost**, **travel time**, and **waiting time** between AVs and conventional vehicles appear with **negative signs**, confirming that increases in these ratios reduce the likelihood of choosing AVs.

The coefficients for **vehicle type** (positive for conventional vans, negative for autonomous vans) suggest that, between a van and a car, users prefer **fewer passengers**, implying higher comfort and privacy in smaller vehicles.

Attitudinal factors—including **technology acceptance**, **perceived social norm**, **ease of use**, **perceived usefulness**, **safety perception**, and **trust**—were statistically significant, consistent with prior studies.

Travel behaviour variables showed that those who typically use taxis or motorcycles were less likely to choose AVs, whereas users who commute by company shuttle exhibited greater willingness.

The **negative coefficient for age** indicates that older individuals are less inclined to adopt AVs, while the **positive coefficient for driver's licence ownership** suggests greater trust in autonomous driving among those familiar with driving.

Socio-economic factors revealed that **full-time employees** and individuals with **undergraduate degrees** displayed higher preferences for AVs, whereas those with **moderate household income (25–40 million IRR)** or **multiple household cars** were less likely to adopt them.

Overall, the model performed well ($\rho^2 = 0.21$), confirming its predictive reliability.

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5. Conclusion

Ongoing advances in AV research and development suggest that autonomous transport will become widespread in the near future. To predict its impacts on transport systems, understanding **public acceptance** is essential.

This study examined the factors influencing individuals' selection of **shared autonomous vehicles** as travel modes. Using a **binary logit model**, we identified that both **attitudinal** and **operational** variables—such as technology perception, social norms, perceived ease and usefulness, safety concerns, trust, cost, and time—significantly affect AV choice.

The results suggest that **transport planners and policymakers** should promote positive public perceptions of AVs through effective communication and awareness campaigns to enhance acceptance.

Additionally, operational variables (cost, waiting time, and travel duration) were found to be crucial determinants of AV adoption, indicating that **improved performance and affordability** will drive their success.

Finally, socio-demographic characteristics—such as age, education, income, and car ownership—also influence AV preference. These insights can inform future transport planning and policy development for integrating autonomous mobility solutions.

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